

BEHAVIOUR OF NITROPHENOLS WITH *p*-TOLUENESULPHONYL CHLORIDE. PART VII. ABNORMAL BEHAVIOUR OF 3:6-DICHLORO- AND 3:6-DIBROMO-2:4-DINITROPHENOLS

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Ordinarily in dinitrophenols the hydroxyl group is replaced by a chlorine atom when heated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and diethylaniline. 3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenol and 3:6-dibromo-2:4-dinitrophenol have failed to give the chloro compounds and also the esters.

Most nitrophenols that have at least two nitro groups in *ortho:para* positions with respect to the hydroxyl group, when heated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in presence of diethylaniline, form the corresponding chloropolynitrobenzenes together with varying amounts of *p*-toluenesulphonic esters of the phenols (Ullmann *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1870; 1911, 44, 3731). Of these two products, the former is more reactive than the other. Both the ester and the chloropolynitrobenzene, so obtained, when treated with ammonia, dimethylamine, piperidine, etc., yield identical amino, dimethylamino, piperidino, etc. derivatives.

A few dinitrophenols and their esters, however, were found to behave differently. Not only they failed to yield under similar conditions the corresponding chlorodinitrobenzenes, but even the esters that they formed were unreactive. Thus, 4-chloro-2:6-dinitro-3-methylphenol (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2481), 3:6-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol (this *Journal*, 1932, 9, 59), 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methylphenol (*ibid.*, 1949, 26, 539), 4:6-dinitrothymol (*ibid.*, 1932, 9, 55), 2:4-dinitrocarvacrol (*loc. cit.*) failed to afford the corresponding chloro compounds, but yielded the esters. The esters also were found to be quite stable and did not behave like the esters of other polynitrophenols.

In the present investigation two dinitrophenols, 3:6-dichloro- and 3:6-dibromo-2:4-dinitrophenols, have been examined. With *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in presence of diethylaniline, they neither furnish the corresponding chloro compounds nor the esters. In each case, the original compounds were recovered. Their esters, however, have been obtained by the interaction of their sodium salts with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride. These on being allowed to react with ammonia, dimethylamine, piperidine, *p*-toluidine, etc. undergo hydrolysis and at the same time the chlorine in the *meta* position is replaced. In the case of their methyl ethers, the methoxy group remains intact and the halogen atom in the *meta* position is substituted. This behaviour does not appear to be quite normal and due to steric factor only, as in compounds like 2-chloro (or bromo)- and 3-chloro-4:6-dinitrophenols, replacement of the hydroxyl group by a chlorine atom takes place under similar experimental conditions.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

3:6-Dichloro-4-nitrophenol and 3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenol.—3:6-Dichloroaniline (20 g.), dissolved in H_2SO_4 (*d* 1.84, 75 c.c.), was diazotised with sodium nitrite (10 g.) in H_2SO_4 (*d* 1.84, 75 c.c.). The product on keeping and subsequently heating after dilution with 75 c.c. of water gave a solid which on recrystallisation from acetic acid furnished 3:6-dichlorophenol (12-15 g.), m.p. 58°. This (11 g.) on nitration in acetic acid solution with smaller amounts of nitric acid afforded 3:6-dichloro-4-nitrophenol (3.5 g.), m.p. 115° (cf. Kehrmann, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 3319). Acetyl derivative, m.p. 89°; benzoyl derivative, m.p. 86°; monobromo derivative, m.p. 135°. With excess of nitric acid it furnished 3:6-dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenol which was recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 146° (cf. Fries, *Annalen*, 1927, 454, 247); acetyl derivative, m.p. 94° and benzoyl derivative, m.p. 118°.

3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenyl p-Toluenesulphonate.—Sodium salt of 3:6-dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenol and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in molecular proportions were heated at 120-40° for a few minutes. The product from alcohol gave colorless crystals, m.p. 121°. (Found: Cl, 17.2; S, 7.96. $C_{12}H_8O_7N_2Cl_2S$ requires Cl, 17.4; S, 7.86%.)

3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenyl Methyl Ether.—3:6-Dichloroanisole (m.p. 24°), obtained by methylation of 3:6-dichlorophenol, when treated in acetic acid with smaller amounts of HNO_3 (*d* 1.42, cold), yielded 3:6-dichloro-4-nitroanisole, m.p. 101° (Kohm and Fink, *Monatsh.*, 1931, 58, 73). This, when further nitrated at room temperature in H_2SO_4 (*d* 1.84) with a mixture of equal quantities of fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.52) and concentrated nitric acid (*d* 1.42), gave 3:6-dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenyl methyl ether, which was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 61° (*loc.cit.*). 3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenol with dimethyl sulphate did not form any methyl ether under usual conditions.

Derivatives from 3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenol, its p-Toluenesulphonate and its Methyl Ether: 1-Hydroxy-2:4-dinitro-6-chlorodiphenylamine.—3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenol (2 g.), aniline (5 c.c.), alcohol (3-4 c.c.) and a little fused sodium acetate were refluxed together for 1½ hours in a boiling water-bath. On acidifying with HCl (dil.) a red derivative separated, which was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 140°. (Found: N, 14.08; Cl, 10.95. $C_{12}H_8O_5N_3Cl$ requires N, 13.6; Cl, 11.4%). Acetyl derivative, m.p. 115°. The identical compound was obtained from 3:6-dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenyl *p*-toluenesulphonate under similar conditions. Derivatives from other amino compounds are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Compounds.	M. P. of the derivatives from			
	Aniline.	Dimethylamine.	Piperidine.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine.
3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenol	140°	118°	138°	148°
3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenyl <i>p</i> -toluenesulphonate	140°	117°	138°	148°
3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenyl methyl ether	138°	110°	136°	144°

1-Methoxy-6-chloro-2:4-dinitrodiphenylamine.—3:6-Dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenyl methyl ether (2 g.), aniline (5 c.c.), alcohol (3-4 c.c.) and a little fused sodium acetate were refluxed together for about 2 hours in a boiling water-bath. On treatment with HCl (dil., 1:1), a red derivative separated, which was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 138°. (Found: N, 13.07; Cl, 10.62. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 12.98; Cl, 10.95%). Derivatives from other amino compounds are recorded in Table I.

All these amino derivatives were recrystallised from alcohol. The compounds obtained from the phenol and its *p*-toluenesulphonate with different bases are soluble in dilute sodium carbonate solution, while those from the methyl ether fail to dissolve. The derivatives from the phenol and its *p*-toluenesulphonate with different bases are identical in each case and are different from those similarly obtained from the methyl ether. This was also confirmed by the mixed melting point determinations.

3:6-Dibromo-2-nitrophenol and 3:6-Dibromo-2:4-dinitrophenol.—3:6-Dibromophenol, prepared from 3:6-dibromoaniline in the same manner as 3:6-dichlorophenol from its corresponding aniline, on nitration in cold in acetic acid solution with a small quantity of HNO_3 (*d* 1.42), gave a product, which after neutralisation with sodium carbonate and subsequent decomposition by dilute hydrochloric acid, afforded a solid, which on crystallisation from dilute acetic acid (1:3) furnished 3:6-dibromo-2-nitrophenol. It was recrystallised from 75% alcohol, m.p. 77° (Jackson and Callane, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28, 472).

When 3:6-dibromophenol was nitrated in cold in acetic acid with a little excess of nitric acid (*d* 1.42), 3:6-dibromo-2:4-dinitrophenol was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 123°.

3:6-Dibromo-2:4-dinitrophenyl p-toluenesulphonate was prepared from 3:6-dibromo-2:4-dinitrophenol in the same way as 3:6-dichloro-2:4-dinitrophenyl *p*-toluenesulphonate (*vide supra*) and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 138°.

The derivatives obtained from both 3:6 dibromo-2:4-dinitrophenol and its *p*-toluenesulphonate with different bases, such as aniline, *o*- and *p*-toluidines and piperidine, in alcoholic solutions in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate, were found to be identical in each case, as shown by their melting points and their mixed melting points.

TABLE II

Compounds.	M. P. of the derivatives from			
	Aniline.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine.	Piperidine.
3:6-Dibromo-2:4-dinitrophenol	135°	141°	145°	132°
3:6-Dibromo-2:4-dinitrophenyl <i>p</i> -toluenesulphonate	135°	142°	145°	132°